

Irish Research eLibrary

National Open Access Monitor Survey: Defining Requirements

Introduction

This survey is carried out under the National Open Access Monitoring project, funded by Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) under the NORF Open Research Fund 2022 to address one of the six priority actions of Ireland's [National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2023](#).

This survey is open until 28th February 2023. Contributions will be actioned upon from 1st March 2023.

The survey is expected to take at least 45 minutes to complete. It is designed to enable multiple partial contributions from each stakeholder organisation/group/entity, so please complete the sections relevant to you/your role, and submit your answers. Please then distribute it out to others within your organisation/entity/group so that they may fill in the sections relevant to them.

Your submission may be paused at any time by pressing 'Finish Later'. Respondents who click on the 'Finish Later' link are taken to a page giving the survey's closing date and a 'finish later' URL. This URL can be used to return to the survey at the page on which you clicked the 'Finish later' link. The URL can be either bookmarked in your browser, or you will be asked if you would like the URL to be emailed to you. **Please note: you are under no obligation to complete all sections of this survey.** The only required sections are the initial questions in which you identify yourself. A download of your responses will be available to you on completion. To view a reference PDF of this survey, please click here [###].

The purpose of this survey is to capture stakeholder input on the tender requirements for the National Open Access Monitor. The tender will be based on the specifications of the [NORF National Action Plan \(2022\)](#), [NORF National Open Research Landscape Report \(2021\)](#), [Science Europe's briefing paper on Open Access Monitoring \(2021\)](#), the [NORF Policy Brief on National Open Access Monitoring \(2021\)](#) and the [National Open Access Monitor Project Plan \(2022\)](#).

This stakeholder survey is specifically designed to:

- Arrive at a community-agreed definition for open access in this context at the national level, and
- Validate, and if required expand on, the user stories and functional requirements of the National Open Access Monitor as identified by the NORF OA Monitoring Policy Brief Group.

The survey sections are:

- Consent (Page 2, Question 1)
- Identification (Page 3, Questions 2-6)
- Dependencies (Pages 4-12, Questions 7-50)
- Scope of National Open Access Monitor (Pages 13-24, Questions 51-70)
- Validation and/or Expansion on NORF OA Monitor Policy Brief Documents (Pages 25-31, Questions 71-85)
- Functional Requirements (Pages 32-36, Questions 86-147)
- Future Functional Requirements (Pages 37-42, Questions 148-210)

Stakeholders, in this context, are defined in the widest sense: anyone with a role in currently or potentially monitoring open access to research publications in Ireland, or who will enable monitoring of open access in Ireland, or who will use the resulting open access Monitor, are all welcome to participate and contribute to this project.

If you have any questions, please contact Dr Catherine Ferris (National Open Access

Monitor, Project Manager) catherine.ferris@mu.ie

Please note: all survey data will be retained and hosted on a third party (Online Surveys) server and not on a MU server. For more information on how and why this survey data is being collected, and how it will be managed, please refer to the [Stakeholder Information Sheet and Consent Form](#).

Consent

1. Please confirm that you have completed the Consent Form [\[link\]](#) and returned it to catherine.ferris@mu.ie before beginning this survey. Please note: if the date/time of the survey response precedes the date/time that the consent form is received, the survey response will be **immediately deleted**. * *Required*

Yes

No

Identification

2. Your name * *Required*

3. Your department * *Required*

4. Your job title * *Required*

5. Your email address (the Project Manager may need to follow-up with you on your responses. Your email address will not be made public.) * *Required*

Please enter a valid email address.

6. The name of the organisation, group or entity that you represent * *Required*

6.a. When collating and reporting on responses, similar organisations/entities/groups may be grouped together. Please indicate how best to categorise your

organisation/entity/group, for this purpose. * *Required*

- Government
- Research performing organisation
- Research funding organisation
- Publisher
- Service provider (including research infrastructure)
- Research group
- Individual contributor
- Other

6.a.i. It is acknowledged that organisations/groups/entities perform ranges of activities, and therefore **your contribution** to this survey may best be represented by another category. If applicable, please indicate below.

+ [More info](#)

- Research performing
- Research funding
- Publisher
- Service provider (including research infrastructure)
- Not applicable

Dependencies

The following questions (7-26) are designed to help align your requirements for the National Open Access Monitor with those required by those internal and external entities you report to, or that report to you.

Dependencies

7. Does your organisation/entity/group monitor and/or report on open access?

yes

no

Dependencies

8. Is that monitoring and/or reporting supplied to an internal or external entity?

[+ More info](#)

- Internal
- External
- Both
- Not applicable

Dependencies

If that monitoring and/or reporting is supplied to an internal entity or entities, please indicate the department(s) and job title(s) and not personal identities.

Internal Entity 1

9. Internal Entity 1: Department

10. Internal Entity 1: Job Title

Internal Entity 2

11. Internal Entity 2: Department

12. Internal Entity 2: Job Title

Internal Entity 3

13. Internal Entity 3: Department

14. Internal Entity 3: Job Title

Internal Entity 4

15. Internal Entity 4: Department

16. Internal Entity 4: Job Title

Internal Entity 5

17. Internal Entity 5: Department

18. Internal Entity 5: Job Title

Dependencies

If that monitoring and/or reporting is supplied to an external entity or entities, please indicate the entity type(s) and department(s) and not personal identities.

External Entity 1

19. External Entity 1: Department

20. External Entity 1: Job Title

External Entity 2

21. External Entity 2: Department

22. External Entity 2: Job Title

External Entity 3

23. External Entity 3: Department

24. External Entity 3: Job Title

External Entity 4

25. External Entity 4: Department

26. External Entity 4: Job Title

External Entity 5

27. External Entity 5: Department

28. External Entity 5: Job Title

Dependencies

29. Are you responsible for monitoring and/or reporting on open access at your organisation/entity/group?

yes

no

Dependencies

Who is responsible for monitoring/reporting on open access at your organisation/entity/group? Please indicate the department(s) and job title(s) and not personal identities.

Monitoring/Reporting Entity 1

30. Monitoring/Reporting Entity 1: Department

31. Monitoring/Reporting Entity 1: Job Title

Monitoring/Reporting Entity 2

32. Monitoring/Reporting Entity 2: Department

33. Monitoring/Reporting Entity 2: Job Title

Monitoring/Reporting Entity 3

34. Monitoring/Reporting Entity 3: Department

35. Monitoring/Reporting Entity 3: Job Title

Monitoring/Reporting Entity 4

36. Monitoring/Reporting Entity 4: Department

37. Monitoring/Reporting Entity 4: Job Title

Monitoring/Reporting Entity 5

38. Monitoring/Reporting Entity 5: Department

39. Monitoring/Reporting Entity 5: Job Title

Dependencies

40. Are you responsible for **collating the data** underlying the open access monitoring/reporting at your organisation/entity/group?

[+ More info](#)

yes

no

Dependencies

Who is responsible for collating the data underlying the open access monitoring/reporting at your organisation/entity/group? Please indicate the department(s) and job title(s) and not personal identities.

Data Collation Entity 1

41. Data Collation Entity 1: Department

42. Data Collation Entity 1: Job Title

Data Collation Entity 2

43. Data Collation Entity 2: Department

44. Data Collation Entity 2: Job Title

Data Collation Entity 3

45. Data Collation Entity 3: Department

46. Data Collation Entity 3: Job Title

Data Collation Entity 4

47. Data Collation Entity 4: Department

48. Data Collation Entity 4: Job Title

Data Collation Entity 5

49. Data Collation Entity 5: Department

50. Data Collation Entity 5: Job Title

Scope

The following sections will focus on arriving at a community-agreed definition on the scope of the National Open Access Monitor.

The opening proposal is that the tender for the development of the National Open Access Monitor specifies that the Monitor:

- uses the Budapest Open Access Initiative definition of "open access"
- uses the UnPaywall definition of "open access types"
- initially focuses on monitoring peer-reviewed articles and conference proceedings
- has the potential in the future to expand to monitor monographs, book chapters, other scholarly publication outputs, open research activities and measures (to be defined during [Action 6.2.3](#), expected in 2025-2027)
- focuses on publications which can be uniquely and unambiguously identified by a DOI
- defines an "Irish scholarly publication" as a publication which contains the unique persistent identifier of an Irish organisation in the publication and/or the publication metadata and/or the persistent identifier metadata.

The logic behind each of these proposals will be detailed in the following questions (51-70) and you will have the opportunity to agree/disagree/propose an alternative.

Definition of Open Access

The following questions (51-58) will focus on arriving at a community-agreed definition for open access in this context at the national level, focusing on these specific areas:

1. a definition of "open access"
2. a definition of "open access types"

Definition of Open Access

Context: the NORF 2022 Open Research Fund [Call for Expressions of Interest](#) specifically tasked this National Open Access Monitoring project to "Work to arrive at a community-agreed definition for Open Access at the national level".

It is acknowledged that the [NORF National Open Research Landscape Report](#) references the [Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities](#) in National Framework Recommendations 8 and 14.

"NFR 8: OA publications must be accompanied by an open licence, preferably the Creative Commons Attribution licence, CC BY, or another appropriate Creative Commons licence, such as CC BY-SA or CC0. Licensing terms should not unduly restrict text and data mining, in accordance with and without prejudice to applicable copyright legislation. The licence applied should fulfil the requirements defined by the Berlin Declaration on Open Access."

"NFR 14: The importance of open archives and repositories for hosting research outputs is acknowledged due to their sustained role in enabling open access over many years, their archiving and long-term preservation function, and their potential for editorial innovation. In line with the Berlin Declaration on Open Access, and via the National Action Plan, Irish stakeholders will ensure that a complete final version of each publication is made accessible and preserved via an online repository maintained by an academic institution, scholarly society, government agency, or other well-established organisation that seeks to enable open access, unrestricted distribution, interoperability, fault tolerance, immutability, and long-term archiving."

The [Berlin Declaration](#) definition states:

"Open access contributions must satisfy two conditions:

1. The author(s) and right holder(s) of such contributions grant(s) to all users a free, irrevocable, worldwide, right of access to, and a license to copy, use, distribute, transmit and display the work publicly and to make and distribute derivative works, in any digital medium for any responsible purpose, subject to proper attribution of authorship (community standards, will continue to provide the mechanism for enforcement of proper attribution and responsible use of the published work, as they do now), as well as the right to make small numbers of printed copies for their personal use.
2. A complete version of the work and all supplemental materials, including a copy of the permission as stated above, in an appropriate standard electronic format is deposited

(and thus published) in at least one online repository using suitable technical standards (such as the Open Archive definitions) that is supported and maintained by an academic institution, scholarly society, government agency, or other well established organization that seeks to enable open access, unrestricted distribution, inter operability, and long-term archiving."

However, the [NORF National Action Plan](#) does not directly align with the Berlin Declaration, as it states:

"We support multi track policies and pathways to open access, enabling both repository-mediated (also known as Green OA) and publisher-mediated (Gold OA) routes, without an embargo period. [...] Authors should retain sufficient rights to enable full and immediate open access via the Green or Gold route."

Therefore, it is not possible to adopt the Berlin Declaration, which requires repository deposit as a requirement to be "open access", when NORF has stated that publisher-mediated open access is also supported under the National Action Plan to 100% open access.

It is therefore proposed that the [Budapest Open Access Initiative](#) (BOAI) definition is adopted. It states:

"By "open access" to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself."

If agreed upon, this will form **one** of the definitions in the tender requirements, to be clarified and expanded upon by the following definitions (questions 55-70).

51. Do you agree with the use of the BOAI definition of "open access" for this purpose?

- yes
- no

Definition of Open Access

If you selected no, please provide:

52. Your preferred definition of "open access" for this purpose

53. The reason why this is your preferred definition of "open access" for this purpose

54. A link to the source of this definition of "open access"

Please enter a valid URL. Remember to include http:// or https://

Definition of Open Access

[The NORF Open Access Monitoring Policy Brief](#) states "Unpaywall is widely used and its definitions are seen as a de facto standard." For a detailed listing of all integrations using UnPaywall, see [here](#).

For the purpose of the National Open Access Monitor, it is proposed to use the [UnPaywall standard](#) to define "open access type", to enable the Monitor distinguish between the different types of open access.

Specifically:

"Green articles are published in toll-access journals, but archived in an OA archive, or "repository". These repositories may be discipline-specific (like ArXiv) or institutional repositories operated by universities or other institutions. Green articles may be published versions or preprints, and can have any license or no license.

Bronze articles are free to read on the publisher's website, without a license that grants any other rights. There may be a delay between publication and availability to read, and often articles can be removed unilaterally by the publisher.

Hybrid articles are free to read at the time of publication, with an open license. These are usually published in exchange for an article processing charge, or APC.

Gold articles have all the same characteristics as Hybrid articles, but are published in all-Open Access journals, which are in turn called "Gold journals", or just "OA journals"."

The [National Open Research Landscape Report](#), National Framework Recommendation 8 states:

"OA publications must be accompanied by an open licence, preferably the Creative Commons Attribution licence, CC BY, or another appropriate Creative Commons licence, such as CC BY-SA or CC0. Licensing terms should not unduly restrict text and data mining, in accordance with and without prejudice to applicable copyright legislation. The licence applied should fulfil the requirements defined by the Berlin Declaration on Open Access."

The [UnPaywall definition](#) of open licenses aligns with this NORF definition:

- Any [Creative Commons](#) license.
- Public Domain / [CC0](#)
- [ACS Editors' Choice](#)
- [APS License for Accepted Manuscripts](#)
- [Open Access for APA Journals Authors](#)
- Many other less-common licenses, as long as they grant users sufficient rights to freely use and redistribute content.

55. Do you agree with the use of the UnPaywall definition of "open access types" for this purpose?

- yes
- no

Definition of Open Access

If you selected no, please provide:

56. Your preferred definition of "open access types" for this purpose

57. The reason this is your preferred definition of "open access types" for this purpose

58. A link to the source of this definition of "open access types"

Please enter a valid URL. Remember to include http:// or https://

Scope: Publication Types

1. The [National Action Plan](#) states:

"Our aim is to implement a sustainable and inclusive course for achieving 100% open access to research publications by 2030 [...] For academic books, it is recognised that some stakeholders may permit embargo periods, but these should be as short as possible. [...]."

2. The [National Open Landscape Report](#) states:

"NFR 1: All Irish scholarly publications resulting from publicly funded research will be openly available by default from 2020 onwards and will be accessible on an ongoing basis. It is recognised that the timeline to achieve open access for publications other than journal articles and conference proceedings, e.g. monographs and book chapters, may take longer."

3. The [National Action Plan](#) states "In the implementation of this plan, particularly in terms of infrastructure, actions should be guided by the principles outlined in the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science. The [UNESCO Recommendation](#) defines "scientific publications" as follows:

"Scientific publications that include, among others, peer-reviewed journal articles and books, research reports and conference papers. Scientific publications may be disseminated by publishers on open access online publishing platforms and/or deposited and made immediately accessible in open online repositories upon publication, that are supported and maintained by an academic institution, scholarly society, government agency or other well established not-for-profit organization devoted to common good that enables open access, unrestricted distribution, interoperability and long-term digital preservation and archiving. Scientific outputs related to publications (e.g. original scientific research results, research data, software, source code, source materials, workflows and protocols, digital representations of pictorial and graphical materials and scholarly multimedia material) that are openly licensed or dedicated to the public domain should be deposited in a suitable open repository, following appropriate technical standards that allow them to be properly linked to publications. A paywalled method of publication, where immediate access to scientific publications is only granted in exchange for payment, is not aligned with the present Recommendation. Any transfer or licensing of copyrights to third parties should not restrict the public's right to immediate open access to a scientific publication."

4. The NORF 2022 Open Research Fund [Call for Expressions of Interest](#) specifically

referenced [Science Europe's briefing paper on Open Access Monitoring](#) as background information for this National Open Access Monitor project. This states:

"Peer-reviewed scholarly articles published in journals are, by far, the most analysed type of academic publication. Standardised workflows of article publishing and discovery have resulted in well developed infrastructures, providing general and Open Access-specific metadata. Hence, scholarly articles are the least challenging type of publication to monitor and have been the focus of every large-scale monitoring exercise to date. Going beyond the scholarly article might require additional approaches to gather, analyse, and interpret publication data. Open Access to academic books is at an earlier stage of development and the publishing landscape differs considerably from that of scholarly articles. To monitor the publication status of books, book chapters, and proceedings, additional metadata are needed. For example, to differentiate between editors of books or anthologies and authors of individual contributions. The infrastructures and data sources for other types are not yet as developed as they are for articles."

Proposal

Therefore, it is proposed that peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings are initially prioritised to be monitored by the National Open Access Monitor; but that the Monitor must have the potential in the future to expand to monitor monographs, book chapters, other scholarly publication outputs, open research activities and measures (to be defined during [Action 6.2.3](#), expected in 2025-2027)

59. Do you agree that peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings are initially prioritised in the tender requirements for the National Open Access Monitor; with the proviso that the Monitor must have the potential in the future to expand to monitor monographs, book chapters, other scholarly publication outputs, open research activities and measures (to be defined during [Action 6.2.3](#), expected in 2025-2027).

yes

no

Scope: Publication Types

If you selected no, please provide:

60. Your preferred list of publication types to be initially monitored by the National Open Access Monitor

61. The reason these publication types are your preferred types to be initially monitored by the National Open Access Monitor

62. A link to a source providing more information about this preference (if applicable)

Please enter a valid URL. Remember to include http:// or https://

Scope: Persistent Identifiers (Identifying Publications)

1. The [National Action Plan](#) action 4.4 is defined as "Invest in Persistent Identifier infrastructure to enable consistent monitoring and improve interoperability". A4.4.2 is defined as "Develop a national roadmap for the adoption of a range of Persistent Identifiers according to international best practice, such as ORCID, DOIs, RAIDs and ROR identifiers."

2. The [NORF National Landscape Report](#) defines National Framework Recommendation 12 as:

"Open access publications should be easily identifiable by appropriate technical means, defined through the National Action Plan. This will include the availability of specific metadata, interoperability standards, and persistent identifiers. Such metadata should be available for reuse under a suitable open licence. Data on citations (references from one publication to another) should be made available as openly licensed, structured metadata.""

3. The [National Open Access Monitoring Policy Brief](#) states:

"Identifiers have a crucial role to play in monitoring, with Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) being the basis for much of the existing monitoring through Unpaywall. It is important that all output has some form of unique identifier. [...] PIDs, or Persistent Identifiers are unique, machine-readable identifications which are associated with a specific entity, output or actor in the research process (e.g. author, institution, publication, grant, etc.). This allows for disambiguation which ensures that there is no confusion between the scholarly output of two authors with the same name, for example. This is critical in terms of analysing any substantial publication dataset. Systematic adoption of PIDs (such as ORCID IDs, RAIDs, Crossref and DataCite DOIs, and ROR identifiers) across the Irish research sector will enable automation and foster efficiencies and cost saving etc. in OA monitoring [...]."

4. [Science Europe's briefing paper on Open Access Monitoring](#) states: "Current monitoring workflows already rely on widely available Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for publications."

"Organisations conducting a monitoring exercise should consider the following when gathering and interpreting data on publications [...] For publications, DOIs are required"

Therefore, it is proposed that the National Open Access Monitor focuses on publications which can be uniquely and unambiguously identified by a DOI.

63. Do you agree that the National Open Access Monitor focus on publications which can be uniquely and unambiguously identified by a DOI?

yes

no

Scope: Persistent Identifiers (Identifying Publications)

If you selected no, please provide:

64. Your preferred method for the National Open Access Monitor to uniquely identify publications

65. The reason why this is your preferred method for the National Open Access Monitor to uniquely identify publications

66. Link to sources providing more information about this methodology

Please enter a valid URL. Remember to include http:// or https://

Scope: Persistent Identifiers (Defining Irish Scholarly Publications)

Context:

- The NORF 2022 Open Research Fund [Call for Expressions of Interest](#) specifically tasked this National Open Access Monitor project to "Work with external partners to deliver reports and a national dashboard **to help Ireland publish, analyse and track OA rates at the national level.**" [emphasis added]
- The National Action Plan, chapter 4 is "Achieving 100% open access to **research publications**", which states: "In line with Ireland's National Framework on the Transition to an Open Research Environment, we reaffirm the national objective that all **Irish scholarly publications** resulting from publicly funded research will be openly available by default." [emphasis added].

Therefore, to identify "Irish scholarly publications" for the purpose of national monitoring, it is proposed to utilise persistent identifiers:

1. The [National Action Plan](#) action 4.4 is defined as "Invest in Persistent Identifier infrastructure to enable consistent monitoring and improve interoperability".

A4.4.1 is defined as "Support the Irish ORCID Consortium and encourage further development and adoption of ORCID according to international best practice by researchers and within the systems and processes of publishers, research performing organisations, research funding organisations, and infrastructures."

A4.4.2 is defined as "Develop a national roadmap for the adoption of a range of Persistent Identifiers according to international best practice, such as ORCID, DOIs, RAiDs and ROR identifiers."

2. The [National Open Access Monitoring Policy Brief](#) states:

"Identifiers have a crucial role to play in monitoring, with Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) being the basis for much of the existing monitoring through Unpaywall. It is important that all output has some form of unique identifier. [...] PIDs, or Persistent Identifiers are unique, machine-readable identifications which are associated with a specific entity, output or actor in the research process (e.g. author, institution, publication, grant, etc.). This allows for disambiguation which ensures that there is no confusion between the scholarly output of two authors with the same name, for example. This is critical in terms of analysing any substantial publication dataset.

Systematic adoption of PIDs (such as ORCID IDs, RAiDs, Crossref and DataCite DOIs,

and ROR identifiers) across the Irish research sector will enable automation and foster efficiencies and cost saving etc. in OA monitoring [...]."

3. "In deciding on what should be monitored, definitions will need to be agreed not just on what counts as Open Access, but on what constitutes an Irish publication. The IReL deals providing open access to many Irish institutional authors rely on a corresponding author's affiliation; this may prove an additional complication over existing monitoring solutions where any author's affiliated Irish institution is used to signify an Irish publication."

4. [Science Europe's briefing paper on Open Access Monitoring](#) states:

"The minimum requirement to attribute a publication to a RPO should be a specific affiliation of any of its authors, irrespective of the author's position in the author line. To attribute a publication to a RFO there should be an acknowledgement of the received funding in the publication itself."

"Organisations conducting a monitoring exercise should consider the following when gathering and interpreting data on publications [...] For institutions, services such as the community-led Research Organization Registry (ROR) should be used. For funding sources, services such as Crossref's Funder Registry are recommended."

Therefore, it is proposed that the National Open Access Monitor defines an "Irish scholarly publication" as a publication which contains the unique persistent identifier of an Irish organisation in the publication and/or the publication metadata and/or the persistent identifier metadata.

67. Do you agree for the National Open Access Monitor defines an "Irish scholarly publication" as a publication which contains the unique persistent identifier of an Irish organisation in the publication and/or the publication metadata and/or the persistent identifier metadata?

yes

no

Scope: Persistent Identifiers (Defining Irish Scholarly Publications)

If you selected no, please provide:

68. Your preferred definition of "Irish scholarly publication" for this purpose

69. The reason why this is your preferred definition of "Irish scholarly publication" for this purpose

70. A link to the source of this definition of "Irish scholarly publication" which is applicable to this context

Please enter a valid URL. Remember to include http:// or https://

Validation and/or Expansion on NORF OA Monitor Policy Brief Documents

The following section will focus on validating, and if required expanding on, the user stories and functional requirements of the National Open Access Monitor as identified by the NORF OA Monitoring Policy Brief Group [\[external link\]](#).

Success Criteria

71. The following Success Criteria table is taken from the *NORF Policy Brief: National OA Monitoring – Appendices* [\[link\]](#)

What indicators would suggest that OA monitoring is doing its job & is a valued, used and successful service

#	KPI	Measure	Importance
1	Usage by Irish Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) to measure funded research outputs	Reports produced by RPOs/RFOs and figures fed into national reports are based on OA Monitoring data	Must have
2	Usage by Irish RPOs/RFOs to measure OA	Reports produced by RPOs/RFOs and figures fed into national reports are based on OA Monitoring data, e.g. the "% of publications deposited in Open Access repositories" KPI in the 2018-2020 Higher Education System Performance Framework	Must have
3	Usage by Irish RPOs/RFOs to promote/enable OA compliance	Public documentation detailing how OA Monitoring is used to verify RPO/RFO OA policy, with corresponding instructions for their funded researchers	Must have
4	Usage by Irish national consortia to inform new OA publishing agreements, and monitor existing agreements	OA Monitoring cited as a source of data	
5	Usage by government departments to measure and report on OA compliance as overall % of Irish research publications	Reports produced by Government Departments (e.g. DBEI, Education) and figures fed into E.U. reports are based on OA Monitoring data	Must have
6	Demonstrable engagement by researchers in using OA Monitoring when assessing their OA compliance	Documentation on RFO websites guiding researchers to OA Monitoring for assessment/evidence of OA compliance	Must have
7	Demonstrable use of OA Monitoring to inform and support strategic developments in the area of Open Science	OA Monitoring cited as a source of data or statistics in national reports or working groups, e.g. NORF or equivalent	Must have
8	Usage by publishers to monitor visibility of published content and analyse sectoral performance relative to peers and compliance with RFO policies	OA Monitoring cited as source of data	
9	Usage of portal interface	Web and/or COUNTER statistics indicating user engagement with the service	Must have
10	Integration of OA Monitoring data into RFO or RPO systems through API etc.	E.g. documented examples/case-studies of direct integration with RFO grant management systems or processes, RPO CRIS systems or process, RPO Institutional Repository systems, other Irish repositories, or processes	Should have
11	Integration of OA Monitoring data into external systems	OA Monitoring cited as a source of data.	Could have
12	Active, ongoing engagement among stakeholders	This is a rapidly evolving area, with new datasets and services becoming available every year. A key indicator of the success of OA Monitoring will be the extent to which stakeholders are engaged and the system is responsive to improvement and critical evaluation through successive, continuous iterations. In addition to more formal feedback from broader stakeholders, the Repository Manager constituency is an important stakeholder in this regard	Must have

Please indicate which number (#) Success Criteria in the table above best apply to your organisation/entity/group. Select all that apply.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10
- 11
- 12
- None of the above are applicable to my organisation/entity/group

Success Criteria

If you selected *None of the above*, please describe the Success Criteria that best applies to your organisation/entity/group. Please use the same format of KPI, Measure and Importance.

Otherwise, please skip.

72. KPI

73. Measure

74. Importance

User Personas

75. The following User Persona table is taken from the *NORF Policy Brief: National OA Monitoring – Appendices* [\[link\]](#)

Id	Persona/Role	Description	Motivation	Frequency of Use
A	Policy strategist/analyst	This user works in one of the Irish RFOs, national consortia, or government departments.	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with national-level statistics and monitoring of research outputs and open access in order to inform strategic direction in relation to funding, impact assessment, publisher negotiations, transformative agreement monitoring, and Open Science/Access	Medium (Biannual reporting, reasonably regular checks on performance or on-demand querying)
B	Research support officer/analyst	This user works in the research support service or library of an Irish RPO	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with ensuring national-level visibility of institutional research and in analysing their institution's OA performance relative to peer institutions, and in establishing compliance with RFO policies	Medium (reasonably regular checks on performance, e.g. once every month or so)
C	Repository Manager	This user is responsible for managing a publications repository at one of the Irish RPOs	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with ensuring OA publications from their system are accurately reflected.	Medium (reasonably regular checks on performance, e.g. once every month or so)
D	Individual researcher	This user is a researcher working at an Irish RPO	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with a) establishing whether their publications are in compliance with the policies of their RFOs and RPO; b) ensuring their research outputs are visible at a national level;	Low (On-demand querying prompted, for example, by funding reporting or quality review process) Low individual usage but lots of individuals
E	Publishers	Publishers, aggregators and related service providers	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with ensuring visibility of published content and in analysing sectoral performance relative to peers and compliance with RFO policies	Low
F	OA Monitoring technical support/contact	This user has been assigned as technical support contact under the OA Monitoring governance structure	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with a) ensuring the system is working as expected through monitoring tools etc.; b) being able to easily answer queries and complaints identified by other users	High
G	External integrations	This is a third-party organisation or system	In using OA Monitoring, they are interested in harvesting records or subsets of records for inclusion in another resource or infrastructure	High

Please indicate which User Personas best describe you and/or the users of the National Open Access Monitor from your organisation/entity/group. Select all that apply.

- A
- B
- C
- D
- E
- F
- G
- H
- Other

User Personas

If you selected Other, please describe the User Persona that best applies to your organisation/entity/group. Please use the same format of Persona/Role, Description, Motivation, Frequency of Use.

Otherwise, please skip.

76. Persona/Role

77. Description

78. Motivation

79. Frequency of Use

User Stories (Functional Requirements and Prioritisation)

80. The following User Stories table is taken from the *NORF Policy Brief: National OA Monitoring – Appendices* [[link](#)]

Brief descriptions of specific interactions with the service, detailing the relevant personas and the features they require to get their task done

#	Title	User Story	Personas	Importance	Category
1	Identify % of current OA availability	As an analyst, I want to be able to easily identify the % of Irish peer-reviewed publications that are Open Access	A,B,C	Must have	Reports
2	Identify OA progress over time	As an analyst, I want to be able to compare the % of OA publications against historical 6 month or yearly snapshots to gauge progress towards OA (to gauge progress over time, you can't simply look at OA availability by year of publication)	A,B,C	Must have	Reports
3	Predefined/Dashboard metrics	As a policy strategist/analyst/repository manager/member of the public, I want to be presented with a visual dashboard of the most common statistics, including a) overall record count; b) overall Green/Gold/Closed Open Access breakdown; c) Green/Gold/Closed Open Access breakdown by year; d) overall breakdown by publication type; e) overall and OA breakdown by funder; f) overall and OA breakdown by institution; overall and OA breakdown by publisher	A, B, C, E	Should have	Reports
4	Faceted analysis drill-down functionality	As an analyst/ policy strategist/ researcher, I want to be able to easily visualise the OA % for publications by a number of facets including funding agency, Irish HEI, corresponding author affiliation, by year of publication, by a given subject or keyword, by publisher, by grant award ID, or an arbitrary combinations of these.	A,B,C,D	Must have	Functionality
5	Evaluate performance of different OA strategies	As a policy strategist, I want to be able to compare the relative performance of different approaches to OA (i.e. Green -vs- Gold) and of different OA hubs (i.e. Institutional repositories -vs- preprint servers -vs- open research platforms) to better inform decisions	A,B	Should have	Reports
6	Export OA classification for further analysis	As an analyst, I want to be able to export item-level OA classification data (DOI, Title, OA Classification) for further analysis, either the entire data-set or for specific search results/filters (funder/institution/year/keyword, corresponding author affiliation/publisher/publication type etc.)	A,B,C,D	Should have	Data

#	Title	User Story	Personas	Importance	Category
7	Compare custom publication set	As an analyst/repository manager/researcher, I want to be able to upload a list of DOIs and have the system return a report indicating a) whether the DOI is in OA Monitoring; b) the OA classification assigned by OA Monitoring	A,B,C,D	Nice to have	Data
8	Grant reporting and assessment	As an analyst/ policy strategist, I want to be able to co-locate publications that have been funded by grants via my organisation/ agency/ department, for reporting.	A,B	Nice to have	Report
9	API Integration	As an analyst/ policy strategist, I want to easily extract data from OA Monitoring regarding material that's been uploaded in OA repositories for incorporation in my organisation's/ department local system, preferably via an API.	A,B	Should have	Data
10	Bibliometric indicators	As a repository support officer/ analyst/ repository manager/ researcher, I would like to see bibliometric indicators (e.g., Altmetric, Plum analytics, etc.) when searching for material.	D	Could have	Functionality
11	Standardised usage statistics	As a repository manager, I would like to be able to easily see standardised local usage statistics for material accessed and downloaded from my repository via OA Monitoring.	B,C	Could have	Report
12	Standardised COUNTER compliant statistics	As a repository manager I would like to be able to see COUNTER compliant usage statistics for activities like searches and click-throughs.	B,C	Could have	Report
13	Author disambiguation	As an analyst/ repository manager/ researcher, I want to see all publications by specific authors regardless of variant name forms and affiliation.	A,B,C,D,E	Should have	Functionality
14	Uptime monitoring/alerting	As the technical contact, I want to be alerted when the system is unavailable and be able to review availability of the system over time	F	Must have	Operational
15	Harvest metadata via OAI-PMH	As a downstream aggregator, I want to be able to harvest metadata records or filtered record sets from OA Monitoring for inclusion in my resource	G	Could have	Functionality

#	Title	User Story	Personas	Importance	Category
16	Documentation	As any user of the system, I want to be able to find succinct but complete documentation regarding: a) what records are contained; b) the criteria for selecting these records; c) the sources from which the records were derived; d) the criteria for open access classification; e) the method of open access classification; f) the governance and history of the system	A,B,C,D,E, F, G	Must have	Documentation
17	Transparent feedback loop regarding functionality	As a user of the system, I want to be able to report an issue with a technical aspect of the system and receive a response in a reasonable period of time in a way that other users can see, e.g. public issue tracker or mailing list	A,B,C,D,E,G	Must have	Operational
18	Transparent feedback loop regarding data	As a user of the system, I want to be able to query or report an issue with the data displayed in the system and receive a response in a reasonable period of time in a way that other users can see, e.g. public issue tracker or mailing list	A,B,C,D,E,G	Must have	Operational
19	Sync with ORCID	As an Irish researcher, I want to be able to sync all works listed in my ORCID profile with an OA monitoring system, ensuring they are indexed and available in the system and as a means of having control over how my work is represented in the national portal	D	Could have	Functionality
20	Periodic data dumps	As an analyst/repository manager/researcher, and in absence of an API or other UI features which allow dynamic access to underlying data, I want to be able to access periodic data dumps/snapshots of included records and their OA classification for further offline analysis, e.g. one every 6 months	A,B,C,D	Should have	Data
21	System status page	As an end-user of the system, I want to be able to access a page which displays the current availability of the system as well as history of system availability over the previous month or year, e.g. https://status.bitbucket.org/ or https://status.github.com	A,B,C,D,E,F,G	Could have	Operational
22	Embargoed access	As an analyst/repository manager/aggregator, I would like to be able to see the % of closed access records which have been deposited in a repository but which are currently embargoed	A,B,C,G	Should have	Data

Please indicate which User Stories best apply to your organisation/entity/group. Select

all that apply.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10
- 11
- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15
- 16
- 17
- 18
- 19
- 20
- 21
- 22
- Other

User Stories (Functional Requirements and Prioritisation)

If you selected Other, please describe the User Story that best applies to your organisation/entity/group. Please use the same format of Title, User Story, Personas, Importance, Category.

Otherwise, please skip.

81. Title

82. User Story

83. Persona

84. Importance

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85. Category

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Functional Requirements

The following questions (86-147) focus on further defining the functional requirements for the National Open Access Monitor, to explicitly define current OA reporting metrics for each stakeholder and required data points. Future functional requirements are captured in questions 148-210.

Functional Requirements

What metrics does your organisation/entity/group monitor or report on?

e.g. number of OA publications by authors affiliated to organisation X during time period X-Z

e.g. percentage of publications funded by organisation Y which were published hybrid open access.

86. Metric 1

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87. Metric 2

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88. Metric 3

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89. Metric 4

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90. Metric 5

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91. Metric 6

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92. Metric 7

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93. Metric 8

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94. Metric 9

95. Metric 10

96. Metric 11

97. Metric 12

98. Metric 13

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99. Metric 14

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100. Metric 15

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101. Metric 16

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102. Metric 17

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103. Metric 18

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104. Metric 19

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105. Metric 20

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Functional Requirements

106. What data points does your organisation/entity/group use to compile those metrics? Please select as many as applicable.

[+ More info](#)

- DOI
- Article title
- Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed)
- Article License (e.g. CC-BY)
- Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.)
- Publication date
- Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM)
- Subject
- Publisher name
- Journal title
- Journal ID
- Print ISSN
- Online ISSN
- Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription)
- APC
- Corresponding author name
- Corresponding author email
- Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID)
- Co-author name
- Co-author email
- Co-author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID)
- Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record
- Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold)
- Co-author institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record
- Co-author institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold)
- Funder ID

- Funder name
- Grant ID
- Funding acknowledgement from the article
- Keyword
- Other(s)

Functional Requirements

If you selected Other(s), please indicate the additional data points which your organisation/entity/group uses to compile open access monitoring/reporting metrics.

Otherwise, please skip.

107. Data point 1

108. Data point 2

109. Data point 3

110. Data point 4

111. Data point 5

112. Data point 6

113. Data point 7

114. Data point 8

115. Data point 9

116. Data point 10

117. Data point 11

118. Data point 12

119. Data point 13

120. Data point 14

121. Data point 15

122. Data point 16

123. Data point 17

124. Data point 18

125. Data point 19

126. Data point 20

Functional Requirements

Which data sources does your organisation/group/entity use to collate the data underlying the monitoring/reporting on those metrics? Please be as comprehensive as possible and list both internal and external data sources.

To note: as per NORF requirements, all data supporting the National Open Access Monitor must be open under open licenses (e.g. CC0, CC-BY, ODC-BY), and therefore it may not be feasible for the National Open Access Monitor to include all data sources currently being used for open access monitoring and/or reporting. The intention in capturing this information is to understand current practice.

127. Data Sources

- Astrophysics Data System
- Bielefeld ISSN-gold dataset
- Crossref
- CRIS (internal)
- Datacite
- Delta Think
- Dimensions
- DOAJ
- EuropePMC
- OpenAire
- OpenAlex
- OpenAPC
- ORCID
- PubMed Central
- ROAD
- Scopus
- Sherpa Juliet
- Sherpa Romeo
- Publisher-supplied data

- UnPaywall
- Web of Science
- Other(s)

If you selected Other(s), please indicate the additional data sources which your organisation/entity/group uses to compile open access monitoring/reporting metrics.

Otherwise, please skip.

128. Data source 1

129. Data source 2

130. Data source 3

131. Data source 4

132. Data source 5

133. Data source 6

134. Data source 7

135. Data source 8

136. Data source 9

137. Data source 10

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143. Data source 16

144. Data source 17

145. Data source 18

146. Data source 19

147. Data source 20

Future Functional Requirements

148. Acknowledging that this is a rapidly developing area, and that all organisations/entities/groups may develop different metrics for monitoring or reporting on open access in the future. Do you know now what the future functional requirements of your organisation/entity/group will be for the National Open Access Monitor?

yes

no

Future Functional Requirements

The following questions duplicate the Functional Requirements questions (86-147), rephrased to capture future requirements.

Future Functional Requirements

What metrics **will** your organisation/entity/group monitor or report on?

e.g. number of OA publications by authors affiliated to organisation X during time period X-Z

e.g. percentage of publications funded by organisation Y which were published hybrid open access.

149. Metric 1

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150. Metric 2

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151. Metric 3

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152. Metric 4

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153. Metric 5

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154. Metric 6

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155. Metric 7

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156. Metric 8

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157. Metric 9

158. Metric 10

159. Metric 11

160. Metric 12

161. Metric 13

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162. Metric 14

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163. Metric 15

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164. Metric 16

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165. Metric 17

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166. Metric 18

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167. Metric 19

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168. Metric 20

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Future Functional Requirements

169. What data points **will** your organisation/entity/group use to compile those metrics? Please select as many as applicable.

[+ More info](#)

- DOI
- Article title
- Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed)
- Article License (e.g. CC-BY)
- Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.)
- Publication date
- Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM)
- Subject
- Publisher name
- Journal title
- Journal ID
- Print ISSN
- Online ISSN
- Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription)
- APC
- Corresponding author name
- Corresponding author email
- Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID)
- Co-author name
- Co-author email
- Co-author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID)
- Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record
- Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold)
- Co-author institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record
- Co-author institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold)
- Funder ID

- Funder name
- Grant ID
- Funding acknowledgement from the article
- Keyword
- Other(s)

Future Functional Requirements

If you selected Other(s), please indicate the additional data points which your organisation/entity/group **will** use to compile open access monitoring/reporting metrics.

Otherwise, please skip.

170. Data point 1

171. Data point 2

172. Data point 3

173. Data point 4

174. Data point 5

175. Data point 6

176. Data point 7

177. Data point 8

178. Data point 9

179. Data point 10

180. Data point 11

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182. Data point 13

183. Data point 14

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185. Data point 16

186. Data point 17

187. Data point 18

188. Data point 19

189. Data point 20

Future Functional Requirements

Which data sources **will** your organisation/group/entity use to collate the data underlying the monitoring/reporting on those metrics? Please be as comprehensive as possible and list both internal and external data sources.

To note: as per NORF requirements, all data supporting the National Open Access Monitor must be open under open licenses (e.g. CC0, CC-BY, ODC-BY), and therefore it may not be feasible for the National Open Access Monitor to include all data sources used or intending to be used by organisations/entities/groups for open access monitoring and/or reporting.

190. Data sources

- Astrophysics Data System
- Bielefeld ISSN-gold dataset
- Crossref
- CRIS
- Datacite
- Delta Think
- Dimensions
- DOAJ
- EuropePMC
- OpenAire
- OpenAlex
- OpenAPC
- ORCID
- PubMed Central
- ROAD
- Scopus
- Sherpa Juliet
- Sherpa Romeo
- Publisher-supplied data

- UnPaywall
- Web of Science
- Other(s)

If you selected Other(s), please indicate the additional data sources which your organisation/entity/group **will use** to compile open access monitoring/reporting metrics.

Otherwise, please skip.

191. Data source 1

192. Data source 2

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209. Data source 19

210. Data source 20

Submit Survey

Please click "Finish" below to submit this survey. A download of your responses will be available to you.

Final page

The survey is complete. Thank you for contributing.
